

Control and monitoring of rice experiments in closed environmental chambers using a distributed network of dataloggers

N. B. Pickering, L. H. Allen, Jr., J. T. Baker, and K. J. Boote, United States Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARSI and University of Florida, Gainesville, Florida 32611, USA

Environmental chambers provide accurate environment control and measurements for plants exposed to natural levels of solar radiation. Our previous chambers (Jones et al 1981) were used primarily to study the effects of CO₂ and temperature on soybean and rice (Baker and Allen 1993). Combinations of environmental set points (dry bulb temperature, dew point, CO₂ concentration) and other factors (nitrogen, variety) allow many different treatments that are maintained continuously over the experiment. Our chambers are patterned after the Soil-Plant-Atmosphere Research (SPAR) units (Phene et al 1978, Parsons et al 1980, Acock et al 1985). The chambers consist of a soil (or, ricefield water) zone (2 × 1 × 0.67 m), a transparent film-covered canopy zone (2 × 1 × 1.5 m), an air-circulation duct, and a control box.

Host system and dataloggers. The host computer is a 486-33 Mhz PC compatible (16 Mb RAM) running IBM's OS/2 multitasking operating system and Campbell Scientific's (CSI) beta-release of its Real Time Monitoring System (RTMS). The four software programs (Edlog, NetCom, RTM, Database) that comprise the RTMS allow one to create and download programs, monitor observed variable values in real time, and collect data from the CR10Ts (CSI's latest CR10). Voltage inputs (thermocouples, radiometers, tipping buckets) are monitored by the AM416 input multiplexer. The AO4 analog output device regulates the voltages to the proportional controllers. The CD16 control-port expansion module controls on/off functions, such as chamber venting.

The nine CR10Ts (8 chambers plus ambient) are linked in a network to the host PC using a coaxial cable and MD9 communication interfaces. Each CR10T

1. Relative enhancement rate of nearly doubled CO₂ (840 ppm) on crop weight of rice at maturity as a function of N application levels and averaged temperatures over the entire growth period. Pot experiment, 1990.

2. Relative responses of crop dry weight at maturity to the nearly doubled CO₂ as a function of N levels. Vertical bars indicate the standard deviation calculated by using the data obtained from 4 temperature regimes.

program also calculates gas exchange rates. Data are collected every 2 s; 5-min averages are saved. The CR10T system is battery-powered, thus main power failure results in loss of chamber control, but no loss of data.

Disadvantages of the CR10 system are the limited input and output voltage ranges and the low AO4 output current, which requires the use of voltage dividers and amplifiers. The RTMS software needs further debugging and it lacks utilities for plotting historic data.

Control and measurement system. External air ducting is used to circulate air over the cold- and hot-water heat exchangers and electrical resistive heater. The cold/hot water system (chiller/heater tank, pump, and piping) provide a constant supply of cold/hot water

(6/50 °C) to each chamber. Dew point/dry bulb temperatures are controlled by regulating the cold/hot water flow through the heat exchangers using proportional valve controllers (Belino KM24-SR). A proportional controller (Electronmatic RE2450AD06) governs the electrical resistance heater. Injection of CO₂ from a gas cylinder into the chamber is regulated by a mass flow controller (Brooks 5850i). Chamber venting, required when CO₂ concentration exceeds the set point (at night), is performed by activating two dump valves and an exhaust fan. Photosynthetic photon flux density (PPFD) for control purposes is measured at each chamber using a calibrated photocell (Panasonic).

Control of small outdoor plant chambers requires strong feedback control and

minimal lag time (Jones et al 1984). All control parameters use proportional-integral (PI) algorithms, and a feed-forward algorithm based on PPFD is used to minimize lag effects. The control performance, based on 5-min averages, is usually within 0.25 °C for dry bulb temperature, 0.5 °C for dew point, and 5 µL/L, for CO₂ concentration. The errors are 2-3 times higher on a 2-s basis. An example of control for highly variable PPFD is illustrated in Figure 1. The daytime PPFD levels are shown in Figure 2. Both nighttime venting and venting due to low PPFD are evident.

Gas measurements (CO₂, N₂O, CH₄) use a common sampling system with infrared gas analyzers (IRGAs) and a gas chromatograph (GC). Chamber gas (pressurized, heated, dehumidified) is circulated through polypropylene lines between each chamber and the control building. There are two additional lines for ambient air and calibration gases (N₂O, CH₄). Each chamber has its own CO₂ IRGA (Siemens, Ultramat 22P) while the N₂O IRGA (CID, CI350) and GC (Varian Aerograph 2400) are shared among chambers. Dry bulb temperature is measured with an aspirated, shielded, thermocouple while canopy temperature is monitored with an infrared sensor (Everest Interscience 4000DL). Dew point is monitored using a dew point hygrometer (Dew-10, General Eastmen Instruments) and evapotranspiration or condensate rate is measured by a tipping bucket rain gauge. The CO₂ injection rate is monitored by the mass flow controller and leakage rates are determined from N₂O loss curves. Ambient PPFD is measured with radiometer (Eppley 8-48) using a factor for PPFD.

Data collection and calculations. The carbon exchange rate is calculated from the change in CO₂ concentration and CO₂ injection rate, then corrected for leakage. Tipping bucket rate and calibrated volume per tip are used to compute ET. Other continuous measurements include dew point; dry bulb; soil (or ricefield water); canopy temperatures; ambient CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄ concentrations; and PPFD. (See Figures 1 and 2 for examples of measurements.) Leaf photosynthesis and light interception are measured

weekly using a small access door fitted with a body glove. Other weekly plant measurements include development, biomass, leaf area, leaf N, carbohydrate, and Rubisco activity levels using minimal sample sizes. Root length density is measured at the end of the season.

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Environmental factors affecting rice responses to elevated carbon dioxide concentrations

H. Nakagawa, T. Horie, and H. Y. Kim, Kyoto University, Kyoto 606, Japan

Enriched CO₂ levels improved crop growth and yield, with a range of responses depending on species and other environmental factors (Kimball 1983). The combined effects of CO₂ and other environmental factors on crops must be clarified to assess the impact of global climate change in different regions and under different crop management conditions. We conducted this study to determine the combined effects of CO₂, temperature, and N level on dry matter production of rice under different radiation and underground environments by using the newly developed temperature gradient tunnel (TGT) (Horie et al 1991).

Rice cultivar Akihikari was grown to maturity in two TGTs for three cropping seasons (1990-92). Air was ventilated through the long axis of the TGT (25 x 2.5 x 1.7 m) during the day; the direction of air flow was reversed at night. The TGT provided a temperature gradient along the long axis for solar radiation during the day and natural cooling of the heat produced by an oil heater at night. The temperature difference between the air inlet and outlet was maintained at about 4 °C throughout the growth period while maintaining natural daily and seasonal variations. The daytime CO₂ in one TGT was kept at ambient level (350 ppm) in all three seasons, and the level in the other at about twice the ambient level (840 ppm in 1990 and 690 ppm in 1991 and 1992).

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Rice plants in 1990 and 1991 were raised in 1/5000a Wagner's pots and spaced evenly in the TGTs; those in 1992 were raised on the ground in TGTs in an underground condition similar to that in a field. Pots in 1990 were rotated twice a week to give the same environment to each plant, while those in 1991 were fixed. The edges of the rice populations in 1991 and 1992 were shaded to create a canopy condition and lessen radiation penetration.

Three N plots (0.3, 1.2, 2.4 g N/pot in 1990 and 1991, and 4, 12, 20 g N/m² in 1992) were created at each of four distances from the air inlet in TGTs. The N levels in 1991 could be converted into 6, 24, and 48 g N/m² by considering the pot density of 20 pots/m².

Air temperature at four distances from the air inlet was measured during the growth period. Crop dry weight and leaf area were periodically measured.

CO₂ effects on isolated plants. The plants in the 1990 experiment were subjected to a radiation environment similar to that for an isolated plant. Figure 1 shows the percent increase in total dry weight at maturity in 1990 for doubled CO₂ (840 ppm) treatment over the ambient CO₂ control as a function of N rate and temperature. The increase ranged from 10 to 122%, with a longer increase at high temperature at all N levels. This is consistent with the results of Imai et al (1985). While nearly doubled CO₂ did not produce any significant effects on leaf area at heading in the low and intermediate N levels, it gave appreciable effects at high N levels, especially under higher temperature regimes (18% increase at 29.50 °C and 43% increase at 30.5 °C). These results suggest that nearly doubled CO₂ raised the optimum temperature for photosynthesis.